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Research Article

**ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE AND TTITUDE OF
GENERAL PUBLIC TOWARDS PREVENTION OF COVID-1**

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Article Received: May 2020**Accepted:** June2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: The aim of this study is to assess the knowledge as well as attitude towards the COVID-19 pandemic between healthcare professional as well as pubic or non-medical staff.

Method: A cross sectional study was conducted between three months January 2020 to March 2020 at different Hospitals. The data was collected by the implementing some sampling strategy and also by the questionnaire regarding knowledge, attitude as well as preventive practices in the healthcare professional, non medical workers and public. There are differnt statistical methods are used to determine the results such as t-test as well as ANOVA.

Results: There are almost 300 people participate in this study including healthcare workers, non-healthcare workers and pubic. The results show that most of the people have a good and efficient knowledge regarding COVID-19 and their attitude is quiet positive. There are almost two third of the participants well known of the mode of transmission, treatment as well as isolation period for the person if had doubt about this virus and also apply or use different preventive measures such as wear mask when go out and to wash the hands when come home and also stay at home. Thus it is determined that there is a negative correlation between the knowledge as well as attitude scores.

Conclusion: It is concluded that most of the heath workers, non-health workers and public is well known about the knowledge, attitude and done preventive practice about the COVID-19. In some participants the level of knowledge is not proper thus there is a need to provide more information by starting some campaign.

Key Words: COVID-19, knowledge, attitude, preventive practices

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INTRODUCTION:

COVID-19 is a pandemic situation which causes most serious and contagious infectious disease (1) of respiratory system. This disease is spread by a virus known as Corona virus and also by the physical contact with each other (2). First it was thought that the virus was spread directly by the mucous contact (3) of an infected person that live on the surfaces, hands as well as objects from past nine days (4). It is considered that the Corona virus and this pandemic were originated in at the end of December from the Hunan sea foods market, Wuhan the main cities of China (5). First this virus affects only Asia but furthermore this virus spread throughout the world that's why known as COVID-19 pandemic (6). There are almost 210 countries affected by this virus (7). Thus the spread of this virus become more easy and fastly because it can spread through the physical contact thus to avoid this spread there are some guidelines given by the WHO (8) and most of the countries implement these guidelines in their regions of countries to prevent the disease (9).

Social distancing, self-isolation as well as lockdown are some major steps that every government should have to follow to reduce the spread of Corona (10). As there is no proper medication or vaccination has been prepared to fight against this strong virus thus the spread of this disease can be reduced by following the guidelines given by WHO (11) and it is necessary to have the knowledge about the pandemic to the whole public and it is considered as the best tool to prevent his pandemic (12). This virus affect the whole world and thus no one can prevent from if he doesn't has proper knowledge about it and tends to follow these guidelines (13). To determine the knowledge

about this pandemic in public and non-healthcare professionals KAP studies has been done and determine that how many people have knowledge about this (14).

METHODOLOGY:

A cross-sectional study was conducted in three months from January 2020 to March 2020. The data was collected by online method a link is shared with the public, health care professionals and non-health care workers to determine that how much they have knowledge about the pandemic situation of COVID-19. The questionnaire designed in English as well as in native language so that in understanding of these questions become easy for public or those people who have no knowledge about the English language. Before the survey started it is necessary to check this questionnaire to determine the quality of questions mentioned in this survey and are they related to the research.

Thus an online survey has been conducted because social distancing is an important factor in controlling this pandemic so that's why data was collected by online way. the sample size was determined by using different software and the results were shown that there is a good knowledge as well as attitude related to the Corona. When the data was collected an important step is to analyze the data by using different tests and statistical analytical methods. In this study some methods such as ANOVA and some other methods are used to analyze the data. These methods are used to analyze the data on socio demographics, medical history as well as knowledge of people regarding their response towards the questions about the knowledge, attitude as well as preventive practices towards the COVID-19. In this analysis method the value of P is lower than 0.5 determined that the results are highly significant.

RESULTS:**Demographics Data**

In this study almost 6000 people take part and complete the questionnaire by online way. The people who are corona infected were excluded from the study and the analysis of remaining sample has to be done. In this sample almost average age of the participants were 33 out of which females are more in number and all are educated involved in the mental stress. The education level of most of the people are bachelors and in the same way the occupation also related with this manner.

Characteristics	Description	Number of participants%
Gender	Male	35
	Female	64
Age	15-30	40
	30-50	53.6
	Above 50	6.4
Education	Middle school	17
	Bachelor's degree	45
	Master's degree	20

Knowledge

There are almost thirteen questions about the assessment of the knowledge of this virus and pandemic situation in different people. The average score for this assessment shows that almost above 85% participants have better knowledge regarding the pandemic situation. The range of correct answers is in the range of 9-12 out of 13 questions and it is considered that if the answers above than 10 are correct the knowledge is acceptable in these patients.

Characteristics	Description	Number of Participants%	Standard deviation	t/F	P
Gender	Male	35	10.3+-2.0	9.2	<0.002
	Female	64	10.6+-1.2		
Age	15-30	40	10.4+-1.9	160.58	<0.001
	30-50	53.6	11.3+-1.1		
	Above 50	6.4	10.8+-1.2		
Education	Middle school	17	10+-2.0	262.0	<0.001
	Bachelor's degree	45	11.5+-1.0		
	Master's degree	20	11+-1.2		

Attitude

The attitude of participants regarding the COVID-19 pandemic was determined by this survey and the questionnaire. This survey shows that what is the attitude as well as perception of the people regarding this pandemic situation. The results that were determined from the questionnaire are given below as

Characteristics	Description	Final success in controlling			Confidence of winning	
		Agree	Disagree	Don't know	Yes	No
Gender	Male	92.1	2.0	5.7	97.1	2.9
	Female	90.3	1.9	7.9	97.2	2.8
Age	15-30	90.1	2.4	7.5	97.3	3.1
	30-50	90.9	1.9	7.3	97.5	2.6
	Above 50	94	0.97	5.6	98.5	1.8
Education	Middle school	91.0	3.2	5.8	99	1.5
	Bachelor's degree	90.6	1.7	8.0	96.3	3.4
	Master's degree	91.3	1.1	7.5	97.0	3.1

Practices

There are some practices to prevent the pandemic situation such as wearing masks when go towards outside, use hand sanitizer and some other practices to prevent this pandemic situation. The results of the survey shows that most of the people follow these practices

Characteristics	Description	Going to a crowd place		Wearing a mask	
		Yes	No	Yes	No
Gender	Male	4.5	95.7	97.4	2.9
	Female	3.2	97.0	99.0	1.6
Age	15-30	4.5	96	96.7	3.6
	30-50	3.2	96.7	99.0	1.0
	Above 50	3.6	96.4	98.9	1.4
Education	Middle below	5.6	94.7	97.1	3.5
	Bachelor's degree	3.6	96.8	98.6	1.5
	Master's degree	2.5	97.5	98.0	2.0

DISCUSSION:

The assessment of knowledge, attitude and practices towards the COVID-19 pandemic among health care professionals, non-health care workers and the public or residents is done during this study. During this study it is concluded that almost females and educated people mostly take part in this survey and during this survey it is estimated

they have a great knowledge about the COVID-19, spread of the virus, symptoms of the disease, attitude of the people regarding the positive outcomes of COVID-19 and also the preventive practices to overcome the diseases. It was estimated that majority of the people have optimistic or positive attitude towards the COVID-19 pandemic and majority of the people suggest

that they will be successful to overcome this disease one day and thus in this way the world can win the battle against COVID-19 pandemic situation. The public follow all the guidelines given by the WHO such as no to go at crowded places, wear masks when go outside and make sure the use of sanitizer and the study shows that above than 90% people follow all these requirements. Thus by doing KAP studies we analyzed most of the factors that are associated with the COVID-19 and thus by this study we also gain a information about that which people don't take more interest in the overcome of the situation and thus don't follow any practice given by the WHO guidelines.

CONCLUSION:

COVID-19 is a pandemic that starts from the last of the December but spread so fastly that almost every country some into this disease and thus this condition considered as the pandemic situation. KAP studies are done to evaluate that either people have knowledge about this disease or not, the attitude of the people regarding the disease and the preventive practices of people regarding this pandemic. It is concluded that most of the people have good knowledge about the disease and they also know about the practices how to overcome this pandemic situation.

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